

Electrophoresis, surface charge and surface activity coefficient of ionic adsorbates at interfaces[†]

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Abstract : Historical development of measurements of electrophoretic mobilities of solid particles and proteins using moving boundary techniques have been discussed in brief. Results on micro-electrophoretic methods of mobility measurements of solid particles adsorbed with proteins and other biopolymers have also been elaborated and features of electrophoretic separation of biomolecules using various types of zone electrophoresis techniques have been mentioned. The corrections required in connecting electrophoretic mobilities with electrokinetic or zeta potential using Smoluchowski relation discussed by Henry, Booth, Ghosh and others have been mentioned. The pictures included in the electrical double layers proposed by Helmholtz, Gouy-Chapman and Stern have been discussed. From the adsorption experiments of surfactants at oil-water interfaces, the charge densities (σ) and diffuse double layer potentials (Ψ_δ) at a given concentration have been evaluated. The data are observed to fit the Stern layer model with counter-ion binding at the charged surface. Ψ_δ is found to be significantly higher than zeta potential.

From the boundary tension measurement, the surface tension lowering or surface pressure Π for soluble monobasic and dibasic acids have been calculated at different values of area A per adsorbed molecule. The electrical pressure Π_e obtained for these acids in the monolayer does not fit the Gouy model of double layer but using Stern model, the extents of counter-ion binding in the monolayer can be calculated. Using the Langmuir surface balance experiments, Π - A curves for insoluble monolayers of different behenate salts have been obtained. At pH 12.0, values of Π_e depends upon extents of counter-ion binding, hydration and other factors.

A new concept of surface activity coefficient based on Raoult's law, and Henry's law have been introduced to explain deviation of Π from their ideal values.

Keywords : Ionic adsorbates, electrophoresis, surface activity coefficient, surface charge.

Introduction

Reuss¹ had shown two hundred years back in Russia that clay suspension suspended in water or salt-water solution exhibit velocity under the application of applied electric field. The velocity of these particles under unit potential gradient is called the electrophoretic mobility particles. It was subsequently realized that the electrophoretic mobility is related to the surface charge density existing at the solid-liquid and fluid interfaces². The surface charge density of the particles is found to originate due to the adsorption of ions at the interface or ionization of the hydrophilic groups from the interface due to change of pH and other parameters^{2,3} in the bulk media. Oil-water system in contact with ionic surface-active agents

also form emulsion due to the adsorption of long-chain surfactant ions whereby the fluid oil-water interface becomes charged resulting in the stabilization of the emulsion system. The charged emulsion droplets in the bulk media are found to exhibit electrophoretic mobility which may be measured using appropriate experimental techniques²⁻⁴.

During 1900 onwards, attempts have been made to develop quantitative techniques for the measurement of mobilities of inorganic colloidal suspension using electrophoretic experiments⁵, Mukherjee⁶ designed special type of calibrated U-tube attached with stop-cocks at the bottom side. The U-tube was filled with stable inorganic colloid below the stop-cock, and upper portion of it

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was filled with the intermicellar fluid (prepared from colloid using high speed centrifuge). By opening the stop-cocks, these fluids could be connected to colloid with formation of sharp boundaries. By dipping platinised platinum electrodes, in the upper clear fluid, the system was connected to the electric main. The electric current was passed through the fluid in U-tube when the boundary between colloid and the intermicellar fluid moved on the glass scale attached to the wall of the U-tube so that velocities of the moving boundary can be calculated. From the measurement of the current density and conductance of the solution, one can measure, the applied potential gradient. Electrophoretic mobility i.e. velocity per unit potential gradient of colloids under different physico-chemical conditions could be estimated accurately. Ghosh *et al.*⁷⁻¹⁰ later on related the critical concentrations of different electrolytes for coagulation of a colloid to a critical value of electrophoretic mobility (or zetapotential) of several inorganic colloids and developed his elegant theory of the surface conductance effect.

It may be mentioned that blood serum forms opalescent solution after centrifuging and separating red cells. Before 1930, different serum proteins could not be separated from blood sera and there was no knowledge of total number of proteins present in serum carrying out biological functions of various types. Tiseleus¹¹ invented an electrophoretic cell similar to that used in classical electrophoretic experiments with U-tube by Mukherjee and others. In this method, blood serum dissolved in buffer was taken in the bottom part of this modified Tiseleus cell whereas upper parts of these cell were filled with buffer that are connected to the serum present in lower layer forming invisibile boundaries. Two Ag-AgCl chloride electrodes were dipped in the cell and current has been passed when boundary between protein and buffer invisibile to naked eye will move. Several serum proteins present in boundary region having different charges and electrophoretic mobilities form several different boundaries. The variation of the refractive index gradient detected by using schlieren optical system¹² indicates presence of different proteins present in the blood serum. For this epoch-making result, Tiseleus was awarded Nobel prize in 1948.

Abramson *et al.*^{13,14} adsorbed many soluble proteins on particles of glass and measured the electrophoretic mobility of protein-coated particles using microelectrophoretic technique. The microelectrophoretic cell was fixed to a microscope in which the suspension of the solid particles adsorbed with biopolymers was introduced. The

cell was connected with two chambers containing Ag-AgCl electrodes using which applied electric current was passed when solid particles in solution moved within cell with a definite speed. At particular depth of the cell, the velocity of the particle under unit potential gradient can be measured accurately which may represent mobilities of adsorbed biopolymers. Bull^{15,16} and subsequently Chatteraj *et al.*¹⁷⁻²² measured mobilities of adsorbed proteins, nucleic acids and surfactants respectively under different physico-chemical conditions. Adsorbed proteins are shown to shift isoelectric points because the biopolymer structure at the interface becomes affected by interfacial forces.

Further modification of electrophoretic technique is the paper electrophoresis and zone electrophoresis methods^{23,24}. Soluble biomolecules and proteins dissolved in buffer was placed in at the centre of wet filter paper of proper size. Using Ag-AgCl electrodes, current was passed through the wet filter paper whereby biomolecules depending upon charge became separated quantitatively. The extent of separation was detected by using colouring agents specific for biomolecules.

Velocity obtained from molecular sieving combined with electrophoresis has been compared in gel electrophoresis of biopolymers. This has been used widely in determining base sequence of human and other types of DNA with epoch-making results.

Electrophoretic mobility and zetapotential :

We find from all these discussions that the electrophoretic separation of charged inorganic and organic particles in aqueous media becomes extremely useful and quantitative analytical technique in the field of chemistry and biology and such separation is mainly dependent on the surface charge density and surface potential of the inorganic and biocolloidal particles present in the systems discussed here. At isoelectric point of protein or at zero-point charge of inorganic colloid, application of electric field will not result in electrophoretic movement and electrophoretic separation of materials since the values of surface charge density and hence the surface potential are zero.

Smoluchowski²⁶ derived an elegant relation between electrophoretic mobility U of the particles and the electrokinetic potential (termed also as zetapotential (ζ)) for the steady state motion of the charged particles. This will read,

$$U = \frac{4\pi\eta}{D} \zeta \quad (1)$$

Here η and D stand for the viscosity and dielectric constant of the medium. Thus from the measurement of electrophoretic mobility, the electrokinetic potentials (ζ) of many suspended particles have been correctly calculated when the solution conductance is high. But when the conductance of the suspended medium is low and the size of the moving particles are very small, corrections²⁷⁻³⁰ for surface conductance, relaxation and particle size effects are to be taken into account for quantitative estimation of ζ -potential. In the rigorous derivation of relation (1), η and D within the electric double layer are shown³⁰ to be same as those of the aqueous system in bulk. This is found to be experimentally valid as shown by Chattoraj and Bull¹⁸. Another important point to be noted is that the zetapotential measured here for steady state non-equilibrium system and equilibrium surface potential Ψ_0 of the particles are not quantitatively same with each other as discussed in subsequent sections.

The electrical double layer :

Let us imagine a liquid system composed of water in which small amount of an organic surface-active electrolyte RNa_z (sodium octanoate, sodium dodecyl sulphate) along with surface inactive neutral salt $NaCl$ is dissolved. Both the organic and inorganic electrolytes are assumed to be completely ionized. The aqueous solution is separated from another phase (e.g. air, oil, solid particle) so that the surface-active organic ion R^- of valence Z will be adsorbed at any of the interfaces between the two bulk phases forming negatively charged surface. The counter-ions Na^+ present in the aqueous phase will be attracted towards the charged interfacial phase by strong electrostatic forces. According to the Helmholtz model³⁰ of the double layer, the two charged planes at the interface with two parallel plates form interfacial double layer. The equilibrium surface potential Ψ_0 at the interface in this Helmholtz model is related to the charge density σ of the negatively charged plate by the relation³¹,

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{4\pi\sigma}{D} \delta \quad (2)$$

Here δ stands for the molecular distance between the two plates charged and the potential Ψ falls from its value maximum Ψ_0 at negatively charged surface to zero at distance δ .

According to the Helmholtz model, moles of R^- adsorbed in excess per unit area of the solid surface defined by Γ_{R^-} is equal to moles of counter-ions of Na^+ adsorbed (or Γ_{Na^+}) in the interfacial phase so that Γ_{Cl^-} is equal to zero.

Gouy-Chapman double layer :

The model for the diffuse double layer was proposed by Gouy and Chapman³²⁻³⁵ and interpretation of experimental data involves surface charge density σ and surface potential Ψ_0 .

In this model, the surface will be charged negatively by the adsorption of surface-active ion R^- on the boundary plane as before. On the solution side of the double layer, both forces due to electrostatic attraction and thermal agitation exist near the charged fluid interface so that Na^+ and Cl^- will be distributed in the aqueous side following the Boltzman distribution principle.

Using Poisson distribution equation for Ψ in perpendicular direction to the charged surface, one can derive quantitatively (vide Ref. 35),

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{DRTC}{1000\Pi} \right)^{1/2} \sinh \frac{\epsilon \Psi_0}{ZkT} \quad (3)$$

or at 25 °C

$$\sigma = 0.3514 \times 10^5 \sqrt{C} \sinh 0.0194 \Psi_0 \quad (4)$$

Here C stands for the ionic concentration (or strength) in the bulk system. Ψ_0 stands for maximum diffuse double layer potential and Ψ , potential at any point within the diffuse double layer. The electronic charge is represented by ϵ .

If the organic ion Γ_{R^-} adsorbed per unit area of the surface can be determined from direct experiments then the surface charge density σ will be given by the equation³⁶,

$$\sigma = \Gamma_{R^-} N\epsilon \quad (5)$$

Using eqs. (3) or (4) one can calculate Ψ_0 for different values of electrolyte concentration C in bulk water phase.

Das and Chattoraj³⁶ have shown that from analytical determination of $\Gamma_{R^-}^1$ of SDS and CTAB for several types of oil-water interfaces, the charge densities σ for these systems have been calculated as function of bulk concentration of surfactants in solution (vide Fig. 1). Corresponding values of the equilibrium surface potential Ψ_0 can also be calculated for this system from the known values of σ and C , using eq. (4). Das and Chattoraj³⁶ have measured electrophoretic velocities of oil droplets at different bulk concentrations of surfactants and calculated zetapotentials using eq. (1). The large difference between potential Ψ_0 (or Ψ_δ in Stern model) and ζ potential in the Fig. 2 indicates that the slipping plane³⁵ for electrokinetic motions is significantly different from AA' (or HH') so that ζ is considerably less than the surface potential of the diffuse double layer (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Plot of Ψ_0 and ξ against SDS concentration in Gouy-Chapman model³⁶.

Fig. 2. Plot of charge density of oil-water emulsions against SDS concentration (Gouy model)³⁶.

Fig. 3. The Stern Double Layer^{2,35,37} : Ψ_0 - total surface potential, Ψ_8 - the diffuse double layer potential, $\Psi_0 - \Psi_8$ - potential drop in fixed layer, ξ - zeta potential, SS' - slipping plane.

Stern model of double layer :

According to this Stern model³⁶, the adsorbed RNa_z molecule at the charged interface may exert strong electrostatic attraction so that a fraction of Na^+ counter-ions at the interfacial phase becomes physically bound to R^- due to strong electrostatic and other types of specific forces (vide Fig. 3). The double layer is now divided into two parts - fixed and diffuse parts. Here Ψ_8 is the potential of the Gouy type of diffuse double layer. In this layer, Na^+ and Cl^- are distributed as in the Gouy layer due to the combined action of thermal and electrostatic forces following Boltzman distribution equations. The total potential Ψ_0 consists of the drop in potential within the fixed part and the potential in the diffuse part of the double layer. Ψ_8 is higher than ζ -potential since the position of the slipping plane³⁶ is different from that of the Stern plane dividing fixed and diffused parts of the double layer.

It may be pointed out here that Mukherjee³⁸ proposed electrical double layer that is divided into fixed and loose parts earlier than Stern using a very simple model and he should have priority over Stern for this realistic model.

The Stern is generally accepted in describing realistic and simple model of the combined fixed and diffuse models of the double layer in explaining colloid stability, electrical phenomena in micelles, hydrophilic colloids charged gels. Further complex modifications of the electrical double layer have been proposed in specific cases in which the combined fixed and diffuse models have been further modified. Assuming these model, binding of counter ions in the fixed double layer has been estimated by many workers^{3,4,36}.

Boundary tension at nonionic and charged fluid interfaces :

At pH near 3.0, organic fatty acids $RCOOH$ are all practically non-ionic in nature. Thus with increasing concentrations C_2 of the soluble fatty acids in aqueous solvent, the boundary tension γ measured accurately by different methods is observed to decrease with increase in concentration C_2 of unionized acid. One can plot γ as function C_2 and also determine the slope $-d\gamma/dC_2$ at any value of C_2 . At this concentration, the extent of excess adsorption Γ_2^1 of the unionized fatty acid can be estimated using the Gibbs adsorption eq. (6)⁴⁰ derived on thermodynamic ground

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{C_2}{kT} \frac{d\gamma}{dC_2} = \frac{1}{A} \tag{6}$$

The solvent component 1 used as superscript of Γ_2^1 stands for the assumption that solvent adsorption is zero so that adsorption is relative in nature. A in this equation stands for the surface area per adsorbed surface active solute component and k and T are Boltzman constant and absolute temperature. For higher concentrations of surfactants C_2 in eq. (6) may be replaced by actively a_2 of solute. For pure component measured boundary tension is γ_0 so that $\gamma_0 - \gamma$ stands for the surface pressure Π in dynes per cm defined by Langmuir^{41,42}.

At pH 12.0, for the ionized surfactants (sodium octanoate, sodium sebacete) in the presence of neutral salt NaCl, Gibbs eq. (6) may be converted to the form^{35,43-48}.

$$\begin{aligned} -d\gamma &= d\pi \\ &= kT [\Gamma_{R^-} d \ln a_{R^-} + \Gamma_{Na^+} d \ln a_{Na^+} + \\ &\quad \Gamma_{Cl^-} d \ln a_{Cl^-}] \\ &= kT m \Gamma_{R^-} d \ln C_{R^-} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here a_{R^-} , a_{Na^+} and a_{Cl^-} stand for active concentrations of the ionic components equal to ionic concentrations of these ions multiplied by their activity coefficients. The kT coefficient m in eq. (7) in general may be represented by relation (8). At constant concentration of NaCl it may be shown that⁴⁹

$$m = \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{\xi_R} \left[\frac{z^2}{Z + \frac{C_{Cl^-}}{C_{R^-}} \left(1 + \frac{e^{\epsilon \Psi_\delta / kT}}{1 + J} \right)} + \frac{\xi_R - 1}{z} \right] \right\} \quad (8)$$

J is equal to $\Gamma_{Na^+}^d / \Gamma_{Na^+}^s + \Gamma_{Na^+}^s$ and $\Gamma_{Na^+}^d$ and $\Gamma_{Na^+}^s$ are sodium ions present in diffuse and Stern layer respectively.

ξ_R stands for activity coefficient parameter whose value can be calculated at a given value of ionic strength. Ψ_δ is the diffuse double layer potential present. Values of m for various compositions of the bulk solution have been calculated by Chatteraj⁴³⁻⁴⁹. It can be shown that in the absence of NaCl, m is equal to $1+Z$ but in the presence of excess NaCl, value of m for most of the systems is equal to unity^{43,46,48}. Also Z stands for the valency of the surface active ion and values of it for octanoate and sebacete salts are 1 and 2 respectively. Das and Chatteraj³⁶ have shown that values of m derived theoretically are close to those values obtained from direct experiments if Helmholtz model of electrical double layer is assumed.

By integrating the Gibbs adsorption eq. (7), the free energy change for the adsorption in ΔG^0 bringing the

bulk mole fraction of solute from zero to unity can be obtained⁵⁰. This is expressed in eq. (9),

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^0 &= -mkT \int_0^1 \Gamma_2^1 d \ln a_2 \\ &= -\Pi_m + mkT \Gamma_2^m \ln a_2^{crit} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Here a_2^{crit} stands for the critical active concentration (CAC) for the surfactant at the bulk phase when the extent of adsorption of the surfactant reaches the maximum value Γ_2^m . Π_m in eq. (9) stands for maximum value of Π at C_2^{crit} . Using this elegant equation, the standard free energies for various surfactants at air-water and oil-water interfaces in the presence and absence of neutral salts have been estimated⁴⁹.

Electrical free energy for adsorbed monolayer at high pH :

Alkali salts of sebacic⁵⁰, azelic, suberic⁵⁰ and octanoic acids⁵¹ are soluble in bulk solutions with or without presence of neutral salt at pH 11.0 to 12.0. From the boundary tension measurements, values of Π for these acid salts have been measured as function of the bulk concentration of the solute at air-water and oil-water interfaces. At a given area per molecule, Davies has shown⁵²,

$$\Pi = \Pi_k + \Pi_s + \Pi_{Cl} \quad (10)$$

Here Π_k is the kinetic pressure exerted by the adsorbed molecules in two dimensions and its value is equal to $kT/A - A_0$. Here A_0 is the limiting area of the adsorbed molecule at the state of surface saturation. Its value at acid pH can be estimated using experimental data^{50,51}. The cohe-

Fig. 4. Electrical pressure vs area per molecule for sebacic acid salts, azelate and suberate salts at heptane-water interface⁵⁰ at 35 °C : (O) Π_c for Na-sebacete (1 M NaCl), (●) Π_c for K-sebacete (1 M KCl), (▲) Π_c for Li-sebacete (1 M LiCl), (Δ) Π_c for Na-azelate (1 M NaCl), (◐) Π_c for Na-suberate. Π_c^G - A curve; Π_c^{BLP}

sive pressure Π_s representing the attractive pressure in two dimensions between the adsorbed molecules in the soluble monolayer at the air-water interface for various values of A can be computed from the experimental data^{36,53}. Values of Π_s for fatty acids at oil-water interfaces are zero due to the two-dimensional ideal solubility of the hydrocarbon group of the acid in the monolayer attached in the oil-phase.

When the charged groups are present at the fluid interface forming ionized monolayer of salts of sebacic⁵⁰ and octanoic acids⁵¹ there will be characteristic repulsion energy or electrical pressure Π_e at the interface due to the formation of the electrical double layer. In Fig. 4 the values of Π_e for sebacete monolayers obtained from experimental data are plotted as function of A . By integration of the Gouy-Chapman equation, Davies⁵⁴ has theoretically calculated values of electric pressure Π_e^G as function of A . Equation of Davies in simplified form reads,

$$\Pi_e^G = \alpha_d C_2^{1/2} \left[\left(\frac{\beta_d^2}{A^2 C_2} + 1 \right)^{1/2} - 1 \right] \quad (11)$$

α_d and β_d are constants whose values are given by Davies at 25 °C. We find with interest that the Π_e measured from boundary tension experiment is considerably smaller than Π_e^G (Fig. 4). This means that Gouy-Chapman model of the electrical double layer is not at all realistic and it needs considerable improvement. Such modification was carried out using discrete-ion effect in Gouy-Chapman model by Bell Levine and Pethica⁵⁵. Π_e^G - A curve with this correction does not also fit with the experimental Π_e - A curve.

We thus find that the difference in Π_e - A curves from Π_e^G - A curve is due to the effect of counter-ion binding by the charged surface particularly at high concentration of neutral salts (ionic strength 1.0 M) and low values A . For a given value of A , the fractions F of the COO^- group per unit film area binding counter-ions can be calculated using a simple equation. This is shown in Fig. 5 as function of different alkali salts⁵⁰. This calculation establishes the counter-ion binding phenomena of the electrical double layer as proposed by Stern.

Surface activity coefficients :

Behenic acid having formula $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}\text{COOH}$ is insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform solution at the aqueous interface. An insoluble monolayer of behenic acid is formed between two computer-controlled movable barriers forming a definite surface area of the water surface. Using a Wilhelmy plate, the surface pressure Π of the

Fig. 5. Fraction F^{50} adsorbed organic ions binding counter-ion in 1 M neutral salt as function A : (O) F, Na-sebacete, (\blacktriangle) Li-sebacete, (\blacksquare) K-sebacete,

insoluble monolayer can be accurately measured as function of surface area enclosed within the barriers. Varying the surface area, the areas per spread molecule can be calculated as function of Π directly⁵⁶ using Langmuir balance.

Eq. (10) will also remain valid for this insoluble monolayer. At pH 3.0, the monolayer at the surface remains in nonionic form so that Π_e will be equal to zero and Π_k and Π_s can be estimated easily from measured values⁵⁶.

When pH of the aqueous subphase in the Langmuir trough is altered from 3.0 to 12.0 values of Π_e for different measured values of Π can be calculated since Π_e is equal to $\Pi - (\Pi_s + \Pi_k)$. These values are plotted in Fig. 6 in presence of various neutral salts and at different ionic strengths.

In Fig. 6, we again find that at given A , Π_e^G the value of the electrical pressure estimated theoretically using eq. (11) based on the Gouy model of electrical double layer is always significantly higher than experimental values of Π_e at a given value of A . Further at a critical value of A , experimental values of Π_e sharply decreases with decrease

Fig. 6. Plot of Π_e vs A for salts of behenic acid⁵⁶; sub phase at 25 °C, pH = 12.0, $\mu = 0.05$: (A) RbCl, (B) KCl, (C) NaCl, (D) LiCl, (E) CsCl.

Fig. 7. Plot of f_1^s (Raoult law)⁵⁶ vs surface mole fraction (X_1^s) for salts of behenic acid; sub phase at 25 °C, pH = 12.0, $\mu = 0.05$: (A) CsCl, (B) LiCl, (C) NaCl, (D) KCl, (E) RbCl.

of A due to the counter-ion binding process occurring in the Stern layer. Π_G - A curve for the Gouy-Chapman diffuse double layer however increases continuously with the increase of A in the absence of counter-ion binding process. In Fig. 6, Π - A curves in the presence of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl widely differ from each other because counter-ion binding and monolayer hydration widely differ in the presence of different neutral salts⁵⁶. We can then write eq. (10) in the form,

$$\Pi = (\Pi_{id} + \Pi_{ex} + \Pi_s) + (\Pi_e^G + \Pi_e^{co} + \Pi_e^{hy} + \Pi_e^{mis}) \quad (12)$$

Here Π_e^G , Π_e^{co} , Π_e^{hy} and Π_e^{mis} are contributions of Gouy double layer, counterion binding, surface hydration and other effects on Π_e . Also Π_k is equal to ideal pressure Π_{id} in the complete absence of other interactions and Π_{ex} the pressure contribution due the excluded area per molecule. Also,

$$\Pi_{id} A = kT \quad (13)$$

Deviation from ideal behaviour of the charged monolayer can be calculated respectively from surface activity coefficients, apparent compressibility coefficients and fugacity coefficients of behenate salts forming insoluble monolayer⁵⁶.

If we assume charged behenate monolayer to behave like binary solution obeying Raoult's law, the surface activity coefficient f_1^s can be calculated using equation⁵⁶,

$$\Pi = \Pi_m X_1^s f_1^s \quad (14)$$

Here Π_m is the maximum value of Π when surface plane becomes fully covered by fatty acid molecules. X_1^s is the mole fraction of fatty acid molecule which can be calcu-

lated from experimental data. Also f_1^s stands for the surface activity coefficient of the fatty acid behaving as two dimensional solvent in the binary mixture in the monolayer phase. Using eq. (14), f_1^s for various behenate salts have been calculated for various values of X_1^s (vide Fig. 7).

Alternatively assuming monolayer to behave like binary solution obeying Henry's law, the surface activity coefficients γ_1^s of behenate salts can be obtained using equations⁵⁶,

$$\Pi = k_1^s X_1^s \gamma_1^s \quad (15)$$

Here γ_1^s is the activity coefficient of the salt of fatty acid behaving as solute. In the ideal state of dilution, γ_1^s is equal to unity at a standard state. The initial Π vs X_1^s plots represent Henry's law constant K_1^s for two dimensional solution. In Fig. 8, γ_1^s for various behenate salts are presented as function of X_1^s .

Fig. 8. Plot of γ_1^s vs surface mole fraction for salts of behenic acid, sub phase⁵⁶ at 25 °C, pH = 12.0, $\mu = 0.05$: (A) RbCl, (B) KCl, (C) CsCl, (D) NaCl, (E) LiCl.

It is thus noted with interest that the activity coefficient terms f_1^s and γ_1^s of the charged surfactants like fatty acid salt represent deviation from ideality when their calculated values are higher or lower than unity. Further, combinations of eqs. (14) and (15) respectively with relation (12) will directly indicate that the deviation f_1^s and γ_1^s from unity are related quantitatively to molecular interactions involved in Π_e^G , Π_e^{co} , Π_e^{misc} and also Π_{ex} and Π_s . This indicates contributions of the different electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces to f_1^s and γ_1^s in additive manner. The surface activity coefficient⁵⁷ a new concept introduced by the present author in gas-liquid and air-liquid surfaces should be expanded to explain complex thermodynamic behaviour of the monolayer phase in most simple manner.

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References

1. F. F. Reuss, *Memories de la Societe Imperiale des Naturalistes de Moskou*, 1809, **2**, 327.
2. S. Voyutsky, "Colloid Chemistry", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1978.
3. P. C. Hiemenz and R. Rajagopalan, "Principles of Colloid and Surface Chemistry", 3rd ed., Marcel Dekker, Inc, New York, 1997.
4. R. A. Hunter, "Foundations of Colloid Science", 2nd ed., Oxford Science, 2nd ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2001.
5. S. F. Burton, *Phil. Mag.*, 1906, **11**, 425.
6. J. N. Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1923, **A103**, 102.
7. B. N. Ghosh and K. C. Ray, *Nature*, 1955, **176**, 1080.
8. B. N. Ghosh and D. K. Chattoraj, *Kolloid Z.*, 1957, **154**, 48.
9. B. N. Ghosh and D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 315.
10. B. N. Ghosh and D. K. Chattoraj, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, **158**, 144.
11. A. Tiselius, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **33**, 524.
12. H. B. Bull, "Physical Biochemistry", John Wiley & Sons, London.
13. H. A. Abramson, "Electrokinetic Phenomena and their Application to Biology and Medicine", American Chemical Society, Monograph Series, 1934.
14. H. A. Abramson, L. S. Moyer and G. H. Gorin, "Electro-phoresis of Proteins", Reinhold Publishing Company, New York, 1942.
15. H. B. Bull, "Introduction to Physical Biochemistry", F. A. Davis Company, Philadelphia, 1971.
16. H. B. Bull, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 190.
17. D. K. Chattoraj and H. B. Bull, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5128.
18. D. K. Chattoraj and H. B. Bull, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1809.
19. D. K. Chattoraj, P. Chowrashi and K. Chakravarty, *Biopolymers*, 1967, **5**, 173.
20. S. N. Upadhyay and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1973, **9**, 17.
21. S. N. Upadhyay and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1974, **11**, 123.
22. P. K. Chowrashi, D. K. Chattoraj and K. Chakravarti, *Biopolymers*, 1968, **6**, 97.
23. R. J. Hunter, "Zetapotentials on Colloid Science", Academic Press, London, 1981.
24. M. J. Gordon, X. Huang, S. L. Pentony and R. N. Zare, *Science*, 1988, **242**, 224.
25. A. L. Lehninger, K. H. Freeman Company, New York, 4th ed. (revised), 2005.
26. M. Smoluchowski, *Phys. Z.*, 1916, **17**, 557, 585.
27. D. C. Henry, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **133**, 106.
28. D. C. Henry, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 1021.
29. F. Booth, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, **A203**, 514.
30. Overbeek, *Advances in 'Colloid Sci.*, Vol. III, New York, 1956.
31. H. Helmholtz, *Wied. Ann.*, 1879, **7**, 337.
32. G. Gouy, *J. Phys. (Paris)*, 1970, **9**, 457.
33. G. Gouy, *Ann. Phys. (Leipzig)*, 1917, **7**, 129.
34. D. T. Chapman, *Phil. Mag.*, 1913, **25**, 475.
35. D. K. Chattoraj and K. S. Birdi, "Adsorption and the Gibbs Surface Excess", Plenum Press, New York, 1984.
36. K. P. Das and D. K. Chattoraj, *Colloids and Surfaces*, 1983, **7**, 53.
37. O. Stern, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 508.
38. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, **15**, 103; *Nature*, 1920, 327.
39. W. D. Harkins and F. E. Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 499.
40. J. W. Gibbs, "The Collected Works of J. W. Gibbs", Vol. 1, Longmans Green, New York, 1931.
41. L. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 2221.
42. L. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1848.
43. D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2687.
44. D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 3743.
45. D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 455.
46. D. K. Chattoraj and R. P. Pal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 410, 417.
47. D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1969, **29**, 399.
48. D. K. Chattoraj and L. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 383.
49. D. K. Chattoraj, L. Ghosh and P. K. Mahapatra, "Surfactants in Solution", Vol. 11, eds. K. L. Mittal and D. O. Shah, Plenum Press, New York, 1992, p. 277.
50. R. P. Pal and D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1975, **52**, 56.
51. A. K. Chatterjee and D. K. Chattoraj, *J. Colloid In-*

Chattoraj : Electrophoresis, surface charge and surface activity coefficient of ionic etc.

- terface Sci.*, 1968, **26**, 140.
52. J. T. Davies, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1956, **11**, 377.
53. A. K. Chatterjee and D. K. Chatterjee, *Colloid Z. Z. Polymere*, 1969, **234**, 1953.
54. J. T. Davies, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1951, **A208**, 224.
55. G. M. Bell, S. Levine and B. A. Pethica, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 904.
56. E. Halder, D. K. Chattoraj, K. P. Das and A. K. Mitra, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2006, **15**, 123.